

The meaning behind the Khajuraho temples and sculptures

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Summary:

The Khajuraho temples are some of the most misunderstood monuments of all time. I explain that much of the misunderstanding of temples (including Khajuraho) stem from a basic ignorance of what temples represent and its architectural symbolism. Once, a temple layout is seen as an ascent of spiritual chakras, the meaning and purpose of temple worship becomes clear. Thus, I argue that the Khajuraho temples are no more unique than any other temple in India.

Discussion:

The great temples of Khajuraho enjoy the unfortunate status of having become the butt of ridicule of ignorant people from across the world. The critics point to the prurient images of humans and deities on the temple walls to extrapolate that Indians were uncultured and backward. Implicit in this judgement is that all talk of spirituality in the Vedas and Shastras are but a mere farce. The fake argument is that ancient Indian culture is hypocritical and no better than the materialistic cultures they choose to condemn.

I have never heard of a response to these allegations. This is until I did some digging around myself. The Vedas and Shastras are all about giving up hedonism to seek Atma Gyana or spirituality. How then can there be a contradiction?

Firstly, the Khajuraho temples are not old. They are only about 1200 - 1300 years old. Secondly, 90% of the images and sculptures are completely about spirituality. Even the rare images (10%) are hidden in corners or well above the viewer's gaze. One needs a trained guide to point these sculptures.

So why should one visit Khajuraho, other than for the notoriety it has gained? The answer is that Khajuraho represents an architectural phenomenon. Huge tapestries of sculptures have been hewn on single massive pieces of rock. The entire temple is made of precise cut, interlocking sandstones placed one above the other. The pillars and rocks weigh 20 tons each. There is no mortar or glue to hold these massive stones together. It is a wonder how the temples were put together. Even the Pyramids, with its simple architectural design, is amateurish compared to this wonder. It is also surprising that such monuments have stood the test of time, lasting for well more than 1000 years.

Coming back to the paradox of morality we discussed earlier, to understand Khajuraho, one should understand why temples exist. One should also understand the basic architecture of a temple. As one enters the temple they go from the lowest Chakra to the highest Chakra. Each

Gopuram or Mandapam represents one of the Chakras. For newcomers, each Chakra represents a state of spiritual ascent.

The outermost wall of a temple represents the mind of the completely unrealized person, who is bereft of spirituality. Such a person is always chasing materialism and hedonism in every aspect of his life. The ribaldry of the outermost wall represents the world such a fool perceives. As one walks into the sanctum sanctorum, all traces of hedonism on any of the inner walls disappears, proving my hypothesis to be correct. As predicted, there are no explicit sculptures as one goes to the Garba Griha (Sanctum Sanctorum). The main temple of Khajuraho, the Shiva temple, has a similar architecture. It consists of five Mandapams located one inside the other. The profile of the temple looks like five adjoining mountains where the innermost Mandapam is the tallest and outermost Mandapam is the shortest. I have mentioned in one of my earlier essays that the path of spirituality is like climbing a mountain right from the bottom to the peak.

If you do not want to visit a temple, so be it. Ultimately, the journey is internal. Going into temples is but a symbolic preparation for the inner ascent one has to make. You will still need to ascend one inner mountain after another till you reach the peak of the highest mountain inside the self (Atman). Next time you hear some wild criticism of Sanathana Dharma it is guaranteed to be from someone who is clueless about what Sanathana or Dharma means.